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*Corresponding

Author:
chinchunishanth86@gmail.com

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Effectiveness of Hip Extensor Exercise on the Level of Low Back Pain Among Post-Menopausal Women in PRS Hospital Trivandrum

Ms. Femifathima T. S.¹, Mr. Pranav R. Kurup², Ms. Remya Roy³, Ms. Sneha Satheesh⁴, Mr. Yadhu Krishnan B.⁵, Mrs. Bency Mony⁶, Mrs. Chinchu S. L.^{7}, Mrs. Karthika Mohan⁸*

^{1,2,3,4,5} Bsc. Nursing Student, PRS College of Nursing, Kerala, India

⁶ Associate Professor, PRS College of Nursing, Kerala, India

^{7,8} Lectures, PRS College of Nursing, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

Menopause is a natural transitional phase in a woman's life that marks the permanent cessation of menstruation and the end of reproductive capability. It typically occurs between the ages of 45 and 55 and is diagnosed after 12 consecutive months without a menstrual period. Although menopause itself is not classified as a disease or medical condition, it is often accompanied by a range of physical and psychological symptoms, including hot flashes, mood swings, sleep disturbances, and musculoskeletal discomfort. One of the most prevalent and debilitating complaints among postmenopausal women is low back pain (LBP).

Low back pain is a widespread public health issue, with significant social, functional, and economic consequences. It affects individuals of all ages but is particularly common among women in the menopausal and postmenopausal age groups (45–60 years) due to hormonal changes, decreased bone density, muscle weakness, and reduced physical activity. In many cases, poor flexibility and tightness in the hamstring muscles are contributing factors to low back pain, as they can alter pelvic alignment and strain the lower spine.

Given these concerns, this study was designed to evaluate the effectiveness of targeted hip extension exercises in reducing the severity of low back pain among postmenopausal women. The research was conducted at PRS Hospital, Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala, with the aim of promoting simple, low-cost, and accessible interventions to improve quality of life for this population.

Keywords: *Effect, hip extensor exercise, low back pain, post-menopausal women*

INTRODUCTION

Low back pain constitutes a significant public health issue in contemporary society, both from a social and economic perspective. It affects a substantial proportion of the population, with a notably higher prevalence among women, particularly those between the ages of 45 and 60. Clinically, low back pain is defined as pain and discomfort localized below the costal margin and above the inferior gluteal folds, with or without associated leg pain. With increasing life expectancy, modern women now spend approximately one-third of their lives in the postmenopausal phase. Chronic pain conditions, including low back pain, are more commonly reported among women than men, and the prevalence tends to increase with advancing age. Low back pain can be broadly classified into two categories: acute and chronic. Acute low back pain typically persists for less than three to six months and is often directly linked to tissue damage. In contrast, chronic low back pain is defined as pain that endures for more than three to six months, extending beyond the expected period of tissue healing. Depending on the context, this type of pain may also be referred to as chronic benign pain or chronic non-cancer pain. Menopause is characterized by the permanent cessation of ovarian function, resulting in amenorrhea. A diagnosis of menopause is confirmed after 12 consecutive months of amenorrhea.[1]

Statement of the Problem

A study to assess the effectiveness of hip extensor exercise on the level of low back pain among post-menopausal Women in PRS Hospital Trivandrum.

Objectives

- To assess the level of low back pain among post-menopausal women.
- To assess the effect of hip extensor exercise on reducing the low back pain among post-menopausal women.

Hypothesis

- H1: There is a significant difference on the level of low back pain among post-menopausal women

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature review is a text of a scholarly paper, which includes the current knowledge including substantive findings, as well as theoretical and methodological contributions to a particular topic. Review of literature related to the present study is organized under the following heading.

- Literature related to low back pain
- Literature related to low back pain on post-menopausal women
- Literature related to improvement of low back pain by various method
- Literature related to the effect of hip extensor exercise on the level of low back pain among postmenopausal women

A cross-sectional study was conducted to estimate the prevalence of low back pain among the women living in slum areas of Dhaka city. The study was done with a structured questionnaire to collect information from randomly selected 60 slum women from three selected slums in Dhaka city. The study revealed that about 82% slum women had low back pain. Among them, 76.7% were married and the majority of them were housewives (46.2%). The vulnerable age group for developing low back pain was 26 to 29 years. Low back pain among slum women Hamp.[2]

A study conducted by the Faculty of Sports Science, Waseda University, aimed to

examine the impact of dynamic hip extension on hamstring flexibility and spine-pelvic movement coordination. The research focused on the relationship between tight hamstrings and low back pain, as tightness in these muscles is known to adversely affect lumbar spine and pelvic kinematics.

A total of 12 healthy women participated in the study. The investigation assessed how dynamic stretching routines influence hamstring flexibility and spine-pelvic rhythm, which plays a key role in posture and back health. Although the sample was small, the results suggested that dynamic hamstring stretching improved flexibility and positively influenced lumbo-pelvic movement patterns, potentially contributing to reduced risk of low back pain the quality of their social and working lives.

METHODOLOGY

Research is a careful and detailed study into a specific problem, concern or issue using the scientific method. Methodological research aims at improving research methodology and statistical methods to more precisely answer each question. In this study it refers to the various steps that are generally adopted by the researcher for studying the research problem along with logic behind them. This chapter deals with methods for the present study include research approach, research design, variables, population, sample and sampling technique, sampling error, development and description of the tool content validity of the tool, reliability of the tool, pilot study, data collection process and plan for data analysis.[3]

Research Approach

Research approach is plans and the procedure for research that span the steps from broad assumptions to detailed

methods for data collection analysis and interpretation. Quantitative research is the systematic empirical investigating of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical or computational techniques. In this study quantitative research approach was used to assess the effect of hip extensor exercise on the level of low back pain among post-menopausal women.

Research Design

A research design is the determination and statement of the general research approach or strategy adopted for the project. Quasi experimental one group pretest and posttest design will be adopted for this study.

SETTING OF THE STUDY

The researcher setting, the physical location and condition in which data collection takes place in a study. The present study was conducted at PRS Hospital Killippalam, Trivandrum. Here there was so many postmenopausal women who was on the age group between 50-60years as patients and bystanders. The study settings were the words of the hospital.

Population

Population is defined as the entire set of individuals or objects having some common characteristics. In this study population consisted of all post-menopausal women between 50-60 years with low back pain in PRS Hospital Killippalam Thiruvananthapuram district during data collection period.[4]

Sample and Sampling Technique **Sampling technique**

The process of collecting a group of individuals or things in order to find out the estimated output through the study. In this study the subjects were selected by purposive sampling technique following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Sample

Sample is a subject of the population that is selected for a study. In present study 30 menopausal women were assigned from PRS Hospital.

Sampling criteria

Sampling criteria is the list of characteristics essential for inclusion or exclusion in the target population.

Inclusion criteria

Postmenopausal women-

- Who are in the age group of 50 to 60 years who have pain over the lumbar region.
- Who are willing to participate in study.
- Who are available during time of study.

Exclusion criteria

- Postmenopausal women-
- Who are taking any other therapies for low back pain.
- Who are participating in other exercises.
- Who has history of spinal cord injuries

TOOLS /DATA COLLECTION

Tools In this study, the research tool consists of three sections

- Section A: Demographic variable
- Section B: Clinical parameters
- Section C: Oswestry disability low back ache index

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Prior written permission was obtained from the authority concerned in the selected area. Purposive sampling technique was used to select samples. 30 samples were selected according to the inclusion criteria in one group pretest posttest. The investigator introduced herself to the participants and objectives of the study were explained to them Written consent from the samples was taken by the investigator. The investigator assessed the level of low back pain of post-menopausal women using the Oswestry disability index and demographic data are also collected by the investigator. The level of pain was classified as mild, moderate and severe. The pre-test was done to the selected samples. The investigator explained and demonstrated each and every step of exercise to the subjects. Hip extensor exercise was practiced by experimental group 20 minutes a day in a week for two weeks. Post test was conducted for the selected samples on 15th day.[5]

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Samples Based on Age

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Samples Based on Religion

Fig. 1: Bar diagram showing the distribution of samples according to religion.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Posttest Results

TOOL		POST TEST	
		f(x)	%
Mild	0-20	25	83.3%
Moderate	20-40	5	16.6%
Severe	40-60	0	0
Crippled	60-80	0	0
Bed ridden	80-100	0	0

On posttest revealed that 83.3% of the samples have only mild pain and 16.6% of the samples having moderate low back pain.

Mean Standard Deviation and T Value of Pretest and Posttest Value

	pretest			post-test			Paired t value	P value
	mean	SD	%	mean	SD	%		
Effectiveness	14.7	2.57	40.13%	14.7	1.69	14.70%	42.33	P<0.0001

**Significant at 0.05 level

shows that the pretest mean score of low back pain was 14.7 with standard deviation 2.57 and the post test score was 14.7 with standard deviation 1.69. The t value is 42.33 which is greater than p value. That is there is significant improvement in the low back pain among post-menopausal women.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study should be

discussed with study objectives, hypothesis, review of literature and conceptual framework. This study was intended to assess the effect of hamstring exercise in improving low back pain among post-menopausal woman. Data collection and analysis were carried out based on the objectives of the study. The findings of the study were discussed in terms of objectives and hypothesis that are

formulated during the beginning of study.

CONCLUSION

The data presented in the study shows that there is a significant association between the low back pain among post-menopausal women and effect of Hamstring exercise on it to relieve low back pain on selected socio demographic variables such as age, religion, education, occupation, marital status, type of family, number of children, age of menopause, duration of backpain, practice of exercise and history of other illness.

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